

NOTES

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Limiting Equivalent Conductance of some Higher Valence Electrolytes

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LITERATURE survey^{1,2} shows that not much has been done on the limiting equivalent conductance of higher valence electrolytes. Since we are interested in the diffusional studies of electrolytes of lanthanide and actinide series, we thought it worthwhile to determine the limiting ionic conductance of cerium nitrate and thorium nitrate since their values are to be used in the determination of diffusion coefficient.

A.R. grade cerium nitrate and thorium nitrate were used and the impurities were not more than 0.001%. The solutions of these electrolytes in the concentration range 10^{-4} – 10^{-8} M were prepared in conductivity water with conductance 10^{-6} Ω^{-1} . The measurements were made with the help of a conductivity bridge Model 31 (Yellow Spring Instrument Co., U.S.A.) which can measure conductance as low as $0.1 \mu\Omega^{-1}$. The cell constant was found to be 1.23 with 0.2 N KCl. The resistance of the connecting wires was also taken into consideration. The observed conductance of $Ce(NO_3)_3$ at 35° and of $Th(NO_3)_4$ at 45° are presented in Table 1. The plots were made between the equivalent conductance

(Λ_0) and square root of concentration ($\sqrt{C}$) in order to determine the limiting equivalent conductance (Λ_0) at infinite dilution for both the electrolytes and are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The values of Λ_0 for cerium nitrate and thorium nitrate were obtained by extrapolation method and are given in Table 2 along with the limiting ionic conductance of Ce^{III} and Th^{IV} .

Fig. 1. Plot of Λ_0 vs. $\sqrt{C}$ for $Ce(NO_3)_3$ at 35°

Fig. 2. Plot of Λ_0 vs. $\sqrt{C}$ for $Th(NO_3)_4$ at 45°

TABLE 1—CONDUCTANCE AND EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCE OF CERIUM NITRATE AND THORIUM NITRATE

Conc. $\times 10^4$ mol dm ³	Thorium nitrate, 45°		Cerium nitrate, 35°	
	Conductance $\times 10^{-3}$ Ω^{-1}	Equivalent conductance Ω^{-1} cm ²	Conductance $\times 10^{-3}$ Ω^{-1}	Equivalent conductance Ω^{-1} cm ²
1	2.20	676.5	0.75	307.5
2	3.40	522.7	1.40	287.0
3	4.70	481.7	2.00	278.8
4	6.00	461.2	2.62	268.5
5	7.00	430.5	3.20	262.5
6	8.10	415.1	3.75	256.2
7	9.00	395.4	4.30	251.9
8	9.90	380.5	4.80	246.0
9	10.10	345.1	5.28	240.5
10	11.00	338.2	5.60	229.6

Cell constant = 1.23.

TABLE 2—LIMITING AND EQUIVALENT IONIC CONDUCTANCE AT INFINITE DILUTION OF SOME HIGHER VALENCE ELECTROLYTES

System	Temp. $^\circ$	Λ_0	λ_0^+	λ_0^-
$LaCl_3^a$	25	145.9	69.56	76.34
$Ce(NO_3)_3$	35	335	249.52	85.48 ^b
$Th(NO_3)_4$	45	665	565.90	99.10

^a G. F. A. Kortum and J. O. M. Bockris, "Textbook of Electrochemistry", Elsevier, New York, 1951.

^b Ref. 2. ^c M. L. Sood, G. Kaur and S. L. Chopra, *Acta Ciencia Indica*, **1979**, 279.

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We have, therefore, synthesised some *N*-acridin-5-yl-*N'*- α -aryloxybutanoylhydrazines and screened for their fungicidal activity against *A. flavus*, *C. sacchari* and *H. oryzae*. Most of them were found to be antifungal.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded using KBr disc. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Substituted-5-chloroacridines¹¹ have been prepared by the cyclisation of substituted-diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acids¹² by POCl₃. Aryloxybutanoylhydrazines have been prepared by the method of Conti¹³.

N-Acridin-5-yl-*N'*- α -aryloxybutanoylhydrazines: A methanolic solution of substituted-5-chloroacridine (0.001 *M*) and aryloxybutanoylhydrazine (0.001 *M*) was refluxed gently for 3 h and cooled. The product separating out was filtered, washed with methanol and recrystallised; $\nu_{\max}$ 3300-3350 (NH), 1680-1700 (NHCO), 1560-1600 (conjugated cyclic) and 1220-1240 cm⁻¹ (=C-O-C). The compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 1 along with their physical and antifungal data.

Fungicidal screening: Thirteen compounds have been screened for their antifungal activity

Synthesis of Antifungal *N*-Acridin-5-yl-*N'*- α -aryloxybutanoylhydrazines

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NITROGEN heterocyclics having an unsubstituted nucleus, are seldom antifungal. However, acridine is known to be toxic to spores of various rusts¹. Horsfall and Rich² found acridine to be fairly active against *S. fructicola* and *M. sarcinaeforme*. Acridines have been reported as anthelmintic³, insecticide⁴, rodenticide⁴, acaricide⁴ and fungicide^{5,6}. Acridine derivatives also exhibit antiinflammatory⁷ and carcinogenic⁸ properties. Compounds having aryloxy moiety have been reported as fungicide and plant growth regulator^{9,10}.

TABLE 1—*N*-ACRIDIN-5-YL-*N'*- α -ARYLOXYBUTANOYLHYDRAZINES*

Compd. no.	R	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Fungicidal activity (Concentration used 10 ppm)		
					<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>C. sacchari</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	H	H	90	90.2	11.8	11.8	11.2
2.	H	2-Cl	280	98.5	18.0	19.6	17.5
3.	H	4-Cl	200	97.6	20.4	20.8	21.8
4.	H	4-CH ₃	185	81.0	13.5	14.6	12.9
5.	1-Cl	H	265	83.7	19.0	20.4	18.6
6.	1-Cl	2-Cl	100	98.7	—	—	—
7.	1-Cl	4-Cl	140	98.4	27.5	29.8	27.2
8.	1-Cl	4-OH ₂	87	92.0	—	—	—
9.	2-Cl	H	225	83.2	19.6	20.8	18.7
10.	2-Cl	2-Cl	88	98.5	—	—	—
11.	2-Cl	4-Cl	85	73.8	28.4	20.2	27.5
12.	2-Cl	4-OH ₂	259	92.7	—	—	—
13.	1-CH ₃	H	182	86.8	13.4	14.7	13.0
14.	1-CH ₃	2-Cl	245	85.7	—	—	—
15.	1-CH ₃	4-Cl	210	98.0	20.6	22.6	21.5
16.	1-CH ₃	4-CH ₃	262	99.2	—	—	—
17.	2-CH ₃	H	170	99.0	12.8	14.0	18.7
18.	2-CH ₃	2 Cl	220	92.8	—	—	—
19.	2-CH ₃	4-Cl	230	86.8	22.0	24.0	21.4
20.	2-CH ₃	4-OH ₂	295	96.8	18.7	14.8	14.4
Bitox 50 WP					73.5	82.8	78.6

* All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

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